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**A Look On Vital Role Of Microbiology In Contamination And Sterilization Under
Plant Tissue Culture**

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The plant tissue culture is the growing of plant cells, tissues or organs on artificial nutrient media under controlled or sterile aseptic conditions. With the help of tissue culture thousands of small sized plants or plantlets can be produced in shorter time duration known as micro propagation. There are basically four requirements of plant tissue culture i.e. selection of explant, preparation of nutrient media, sterilization and culturing of explant (i.e. regeneration or organogenesis). Here we are going to discuss two main success determining factors firstly, preparation and selection of suitable nutrient media secondly sterilization techniques for explants. Nutrient media or tissue culture media is the source of nutrition which helps in the growth and establishment of explant. Composition of the culture media is dependent on two factors i.e. the particular species of a plant, and the type of material used for culture such as cells, tissues, organs, protoplast, etc. Depending on the requirement media used may be either solid or liquid and can be obtained naturally or may be composed of chemicals called as synthetic media. Basic components of culture media are macronutrients, micronutrients, carbon sources, Iron (as chelating agent), vitamins, plant growth regulators and hormones, organic nitrogen and agar (if need to grow in solid media). Other factors include temperature, pH, photoperiod should also be maintained during tissue culture along with nutrient media. Next

significant part is sterilization, refers killing of microbes to maintain aseptic condition during tissue culture. Contamination is a common problem in tissue culture that affects the yield of cultured plants. Therefore, sterilization is the primary requirement of tissue culture. It very much determines the success percentage of the process and impacts the production of the end products. Sterilization can be achieved by a combination of heat, chemicals, filtration, UV rays, chlorine dioxide gas etc. Through this paper we are going to discuss different explant sterilization techniques. Sterilization of explant is done by surface sterilization method by using different sterilizing agents like Mercuric chloride, ethanol, sodium hypochlorite etc. Keywords: Population, growth media, physical factors, growth regulators, contamination